

Original Article

Publication History:

Published 1/1/2021

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.4417004

Corresponding Author:

Dr. Qudsia Amir, DHQ
teaching hospital Sargodha
amir.qudsia@gmail.com

Cite this article as:

Haq IU, Khalid S, Amir Q.
Prevalence of jaundice
among patients presenting
in outdoor department. Int.
J. Med. Dent. Allied Health
Sci. 2021;3(1). 697-701

© Copyright 2020

This is an open access article
distributed under the terms of the
Creative Commons Attribution
License CC-BY 4.0., which
permits unrestricted use,
distribution, and reproduction in
any medium, provided the
original author and source are
credited.

**PREVALENCE OF JAUNDICE AMONG
PATIENTS PRESENTING IN OUTDOOR
DEPARTMENT**

AUTHORS:

1. DR. IHTISHAM UL HAQ, PRIME FOUNDATION,
MERGED AERA RETURNEES SUPPORT
PROGRAM
2. DR. SOBIA KHALID, DHQ TEACHING
HOSPITAL SARGODHA
3. DR. QUDSIA AMIR, DHQ TEACHING HOSPITAL
SARGODHA

ABSTRACT:

Jaundice, also known as icterus, is a yellowish or greenish pigmentation of the skin and whites of the eyes due to high bilirubin levels. Jaundice in adults is typically a sign indicating the presence of underlying diseases involving abnormal heme metabolism, liver dysfunction, or biliary tract obstruction. This cross-sectional study was conducted among the patients presenting in outdoor department of different hospitals. Name, age, gender, and history of presentation and disease duration were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. There were 70 patients included in this study i.e., 35 males (50%) and 35 females (50%). The mean age of the patients was 29.23±3.21 years. The minimum age was 19 years and maximum age was 35 years. Out of 70 patients nine patients presented with jaundice. Further workup was advised for these patients.

KEYWORDS: JAUNDICE

INTRODUCTION:

Jaundice, also known as icterus, is a yellowish or greenish pigmentation of the skin and whites of the eyes due to high bilirubin levels. Jaundice in adults is typically a sign indicating the presence of underlying diseases involving abnormal heme metabolism, liver dysfunction, or biliary tract obstruction. The prevalence of jaundice in adults is rare, while jaundice in babies is common with an estimated 80% affected during their first week of life. The most commonly associated symptoms of jaundice are itchiness, pale feces, and dark urine. Normal levels of bilirubin in blood are below 1.0 mg/dl (17 μ mol/l), while levels over 2–3 mg/dl (34-51 μ mol/l) typically result in jaundice. High blood bilirubin is divided into two types - unconjugated bilirubin and conjugated bilirubin. Causes of jaundice vary from nonserious to potentially fatal. High unconjugated bilirubin may be due to excess red blood cell breakdown, large bruises, genetic conditions such as Gilbert's syndrome, not eating for a prolonged period of time, newborn jaundice, or thyroid problems. High conjugated bilirubin may be due to liver diseases such as cirrhosis or hepatitis, infections, medications, or blockage of the bile duct. Blockage of the bile duct may occur due to gallstones, cancer, or pancreatitis. Other conditions can also cause yellowish skin, but are not jaundice, including carotenemia — which can develop from eating large amounts of foods containing carotene — or medications such as rifampin.

Treatment of jaundice is typically determined by the underlying cause. If a bile duct blockage is present, surgery is typically required; otherwise, management is medical. Medical management may involve treating infectious causes and stopping medication that could be contributing to the jaundice. Jaundice in newborns may be treated with phototherapy or exchanged transfusion depending on age and prematurity when the bilirubin is greater than 4–21 mg/dl (68-360 μ mol/l). The itchiness may be helped by draining the gallbladder or ursodeoxycholic acid. The word "jaundice" is from the French jaunisse, meaning "yellow disease".

The most common signs of jaundice in adults are a yellowish discoloration of the white area of the eye (sclera) and skin with scleral icterus presence indicating a serum bilirubin of at least 3 mg/dl. Other common signs include dark urine (bilirubinuria) and pale, (acholia) fatty stool (steatorrhea). Because bilirubin is a skin irritant, jaundice is commonly associated with severe itchiness (1-3). The objective of this study was to see the prevalence of jaundice among the patients presenting in outdoor department.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted among the patients presenting in outdoor department of different hospitals. Name, age, gender, and history of presentation and disease duration were noted on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analyzed with SPSS Ver. 23.0. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviation. The qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentages.

RESULTS:

There were 70 patients included in this study i.e., 35 males (50%) and 35 females (50%). The mean age of the patients was 29.23 ± 3.21 years. The minimum age was 19 years and maximum age was 35 years. Out of 70 patients nine patients presented with jaundice. Further workup was advised for these patients.

DISCUSSION:

Jaundice in adults is rare. Under the five year DISCOVERY programme in the UK, annual incidence of jaundice was 0.74 per 1000 individuals over age 45, although this rate may be slightly inflated due to the main goal of the programme collecting and analyzing cancer data in the population. Jaundice is commonly associated with severity of disease with an incidence of up to 40% of patients requiring intensive care in ICU experiencing jaundice. The causes of jaundice in the intensive care setting is both due to jaundice as the

primary reason for ICU stay or as a morbidity to an underlying disease (i.e. sepsis). In the developed world, the most common causes of jaundice are blockage of the bile duct or medication-induced. In the developing world, the most common cause of jaundice is infectious such as viral hepatitis, leptospirosis, schistosomiasis, or malaria.

Treatment of jaundice will vary depending on the underlying cause. If a bile duct blockage is present, surgery is typically required; otherwise, management will be medical. Surgery in patients with obstructive jaundice are associated with significantly higher rates of complications (69% vs 38%, $P=0.002$) and mortality. Medical management may involve treating infectious causes and stopping medication that could be contributing to the jaundice. The itchiness may be helped by draining the gallbladder or ursodeoxycholic acid. Hyperbilirubinemia, more precisely hyperbilirubinemia due to the unconjugated fraction, may cause bilirubin to accumulate in the gray matter of the central nervous system, potentially causing irreversible neurological damage leading to a condition known as kernicterus. Depending on the level of exposure, the effects range from unnoticeable to severe brain damage and even death. Newborns are especially vulnerable to hyperbilirubinemia-induced neurological damage and therefore must be carefully monitored for alterations in their serum bilirubin levels. Individuals with parenchymal liver disease who have impaired hemostasis may develop bleeding problems.

Risk factors associated with high serum bilirubin levels include male gender, white ethnicities, and active smoking. Mean serum total bilirubin levels in adults were found to be higher in men (0.72 ± 0.004 mg/dL) than women (0.52 ± 0.003 mg/dL). Higher bilirubin levels in adults are found also in non-Hispanic white population (0.63 ± 0.004 mg/dL) and Mexican American population (0.61 ± 0.005 mg/dL) while lower in non-Hispanic black population (0.55 ± 0.005 mg/dL). Bilirubin levels are higher in active smokers (4-6).

REFERENCES:

1. Dixon, Elijah; Vollmer, Charles M.; May, Gary R., eds. (2015). Management of Benign Biliary Stenosis and Injury. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-22273-8. ISBN 978-3-319-22272-1.
2. ^ Lorenz, Jonathan (2016-10-31). "Management of Malignant Biliary Obstruction". *Seminars in Interventional Radiology*. 33 (4): 259–267. doi:10.1055/s-0036-1592330. ISSN 0739-9529. PMC 5088103. PMID 27904244.
3. ^ Zhang, Lulu; Sanagapalli, Santosh; Stoita, Alina (2018-05-21). "Challenges in diagnosis of pancreatic cancer". *World Journal of Gastroenterology*. 24 (19): 2047–2060. doi:10.3748/wjg.v24.i19.2047. ISSN 1007-9327. PMC 5960811. PMID 29785074.
4. ^ Jump up to:a b Björnsson, Einar; Gustafsson, Jonas; Borkman, Jakob; Kilander, Anders (2008). "Fate of patients with obstructive jaundice". *Journal of Hospital Medicine*. 3 (2): 117–123. doi:10.1002/jhm.272. ISSN 1553-5592. PMID 18438808.
5. ^ Neville BW (2012). *Oral and Maxillofacial Pathology* (3rd ed.). Singapore: Elsevier. p. 798. ISBN 9789814371070.
6. ^ Ahmad J, Friedman SL, Dancygier H (2014). *Mount Sinai Expert Guides: Hepatology*. John Wiley & Sons. ISBN 9781118742525. Archived from the original on 2017-09-08.